

Crop yield estimation using deep learning

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Abstract

Effective crop load management in orchards is a requirement for accurate crop yield estimation. Traditionally this involves various methods of obtaining a measure of the fruit tree features that predominantly determine crop yield (wood, buds, flowers, fruitlets, and fruit). Manual counting of fruit, flowers, or fruitlets during various stages of growth is a laborious and expensive process and often suffers from significant inaccuracies. While optical approaches to automated fruit counting have been proposed they are usually not robust to changing light conditions or colour and shape changes of the fruit during the growing season.

We are currently developing an automated yield estimation system that optically estimates crop yield in orchards during various stages of growth. Instead of using traditional machine vision and image processing algorithms we build on recent advances in convolutional neural networks (CNN) to build an object detector that extracts regions from the image that represent a fruit. The same framework can also be used to detect leaves, branches or other parts of the orchard canopy. These results can then be used to estimate yield using a statistical modelling approach.

Introduction

To survive as a species in unpredictable environments, most fruit crops (on trees, vines) produce a plethora of their yield components like buds, flowers and fruits (Gene Albrigo et al., 2002). Typically the actual counts of such yield components exceed the final agronomical optimal target numbers of fruits by 10 to 20 fold. Fruit growers manage these capacities mainly with training and pruning the wood (canes, vines). In some crops (e.g. kiwi fruits, apples) growers also reduce flowers or later fruitlets to manage the load to the plant imposed by the crop (Robinson, 2008). The purposeful reduction of flowers or later fruitlets is called 'thinning'.

Managing the crop load of vines or trees intends to use our current understanding of the maximal ('potential') and optimal carrying capacity as an optimal combination of fruit number and fruit size. To target that optimal 'crop load' (Racskó, 2006), e.g. by adjusting the number of fruitlets per apple tree, requires having a good understanding of the actual fruitlet number of the group of trees to be 'thinned' (Weibel et al., 2012). Currently growers count fruitlets manually on selected trees and deduct their decisions on averaged fruitlet numbers per block of fruit trees (Pflanz et al., 2014). However the variability of such yield components can exceed 100% between trees of one row or within a block of trees. Therefore higher numbers of samples of fruitlet counts are needed.

Sensing technologies are required that allow to count these yield components on a more precise way, automatically and at many more sites within an orchard. Various projects are looking into the possibilities to use machine vision systems to identify flowers or fruits within canopies (e.g. Dorj, 2017; Song et al., 2014; Stajnko et al., 2009). Most of these approaches use traditional methods of image analysis by segmentation of flowers or fruits from the image background based on geometric features (shape, form, size) and in some instances a combination with texture differences (Pothens et al., 2016). However, these methods have only limited accuracy in detecting the objects in the canopies (Bargoti et al., 2017). New methods are required for more accurate discrimination of flowers or fruitlets (Cheng et al., 2017).

Methods

We use a deep convolutional neural network (DCNN) as the basis of our fruit detection algorithm. DCNNs are a type of deep neural network that has become very popular in machine vision and especially the automatic classification of images (Xie et al., 2017). Convolutional neural networks (CNN) are a type of feed-forward artificial neural network that uses neurons organised so that there is a spatial overlap between neurons. This spatial overlap is called the receptive field of the layer that those neurons are present in and takes advantage of the fact that areas of interest in images are typically spatially clustered on the image plane (Ciresan et al., 2011). Mathematically, the operation of feeding an image through such a layer of spatially overlapping neurons is equivalent to convolution hence the name.

DCNNs are CNNs that are multiple layers deep. By adding multiple layers of neurons in a sequence the ability of the network to learn complex patterns in images are greatly enhanced. This stacked layering of neurons called feature maps are illustrated Figure 1.

Figure 1. Multiple convolutions and sub-sampling of images are stacked in a sequence creating a complex network (image source: Wikimedia Commons).

A pre-trained CNN has already has its weights trained to extract useful features from images and ultimately classify them into potentially hundreds of image categories. For example, one can download the InceptionV3 model as a CNN that has been trained on the ImageNet image dataset (Szegedy et al., 2016) (Szegedy et al., 2016). ImageNet is a giant database of annotated images made publically available to researchers (see <http://image-net.org>). As of May 2017 the ImageNet dataset contains over 14 million labelled images covering thousands of image classes.

ImageNet provides enough diverse image data to train large models like InceptionV3 to become very good at extracting useful features from generic images for classification purposes. These extracted features can then be used to train a simple linear regressor to classify these features into pre-defined image classes. A diagram of the InceptionV3 model that highlights the model architecture is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The InceptionV3 model contains several layers of convolution and pooling modules and once properly trained can be used as a generic feature extractor for classifying images (image source: Google Research).

However, as the complexity of the network increases with additional layers, so also does the need for labelled image data to train the network. These networks can only find patterns in data when provided with a sufficient number of correctly classified examples to train on. For example, a network that is trained to classify parts of an image as containing a fruit, or not, need many examples of fruit and non-fruit areas for training before it can be used as a fruit detector. These examples need to be correctly labelled, manually or by some other means, as either a positive fruit match or a negative match.

For complex networks creating such a labelled dataset of image examples is a massive, labour intensive job since adequate training often requires thousands or even millions of labelled images. In this project collecting such a dataset would not have been possible so we take advantage of publically available CCNs that have been pre-trained on large image datasets.

For our application we used the InceptionV3 model pre-trained on the ImageNet database as a generic image feature extractor and then added our own classifier to it for classifying parts of an image as containing a fruit or background features. This approach is known as transfer learning and the main idea is to take a pre-trained classifier network, like InceptionV3, and replace the final layer of the network with one that we train ourselves on our own custom dataset of images. The final layer of the network is known as the classification head and can be trained separately from the rest of the network using custom images not seen by the rest of the network. Training the classification head in isolation is much faster and requires much less training data than training of the entire network. This allows us to build a powerful classifier without the requirement of a massive image dataset. The transfer learning approach as it applies to our application is illustrated in Figure 3.

At this point our fruit classifier network can only classify images as being either of a target fruit or not. It is not able to analyse an image and detect where all the fruit are present in the image. This is known as the localisation problem and solving it is required for a system that can count the number of fruit present in an image. This ability to count fruit from images of orchard canopies is a key to our yield estimation system.

Figure 3. In most CNN architectures the final layer of the network takes the features extracted by the previous convolution layers and classifies them into image classes. We replace this final layer with a classifier we train ourselves on fruit images.

In order to turn our classifier network into one that can localise and count individual fruit we again take advantage of the network architecture of the CNN. In most CNNs convolution and pooling layers are sequentially applied to the input image turning the high resolution input into lower resolution representations where spatially correlated clusters of pixels are pooled together to form high dimensional feature vectors associated with different parts of the input image. As more of these layers

are added the spatial resolution of the representation is decreased but the dimensionality of the feature vectors that represent each spatial area is increased and becomes more descriptive. Once enough layers are added the remaining spatial correlated outputs are pooled into a single high-dimensional feature vector that is sent to the classification head. However, before this final pooling occurs we take the output of the last convolution layer and without further pooling use it as input to our custom classifier head.

Without pooling, the output of the last convolution layer is a grid of spatially correlated feature vectors of the same dimension as the output of the network till just before the classification head (see Figure 4). We can therefore treat each element in the grid as a separate output to be classified by the classification head. In this way the grid represents a map of where in the image evidence for the final classification comes from and if the grid is fine enough it can be used to localise individual fruit in an image.

Figure 4. The final layers of the InceptionV3 network consist of a final convolution layer followed by a pooling layer and a classification head. We use the output of the last convolution layer as input to our localiser.

Our prototype localiser uses the classifier outputs from each of these elements in the grid to build bounding boxes for individual fruit or, as is often the case, clusters of fruit that are close together. Since each classifier output represents a confidence value that the corresponding part of the image contains a fruit we threshold on these value so that the highest confidence areas form the inside of our bounding boxes. This process is illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5. The output from the localiser is a grid of confidence scores that indicate where in the image the classifier predicts the presence of fruit. In the top image this grid is represented as coloured squares with red indicating the highest confidence and blue the lowest. By thresholding on these scores we can generate bounding boxes as shown in the bottom image.

In order to train the custom classifier head we have to provide it with images of fruit in the context of the canopy images that we want to use as input for our fruit detector/localiser. In this case we are training a binary classifier since all regions in the canopy should either be classified as fruit or non-fruit. We manually select several areas of interest in the canopy image and label them as either containing fruit or not. These areas are then extracted from the image, resized, and normalised. This ensures they all have the same size and extents for using a training data for our custom classifier head. The labelling process is illustrated in Figure 6.

The labelling process needs to be carefully managed so that examples of both fruit and background are collected in a way that covers as many as possible different ways they can appear in orchard canopy images. This means that fruit in multiple orientations, different sizes, different light conditions, and different occlusions need to be represented in the training set. Furthermore, non-fruit background areas have to be collected to cover a diverse range of objects including leaves, branches, sky, ground, posts, plastic tags, and many other objects that can be present in the image. It is challenging to create these datasets for training but we found by using a well prepared pre-trained network like InceptionV3 as our feature extractor we can get good results even with very limited training data.

Figure 6. Areas of interest are manually selected and labelled to create a training dataset. In this example all the grape bunches are labelled in a vineyard canopy image.

Results

As this is still an early stage of the project we have yet to compare our localisation results with manually harvested ground-truth data. We have processed images from apple orchards and grape vineyards and created several small datasets to train our classifier head on.

From images collected at an apple orchard we selected 21 images of the canopy that covers several different light conditions and views of the canopy. The resolution of the images is 2000x3000 pixels and all images were normalised to the same mean intensity in each of the 3 colour channels (red, blue, green). In this dataset all the images were captured over a period of two days and so all the fruit are roughly at the same stage of growth. An example of an unprocessed canopy image is shown in Figure 7.

After processing and labelling of these 21 images 442 areas of interest are extracted and forms the basis of our training set. To improve training performance a technique called data augmentation is used to randomly transform our image data by applying random rotations, flips, and shears to the images and adding the transformed images as extra images to train on. This increases the size of our training data without having to process any more images. Even though the generated images are correlated with their source images the network still gains from seeing the same image in a different orientation and it guards the network from overfitting to a small dataset. In Figure 8 some of the processed areas of interest are illustrated as a mosaic of labelled images.

This was our smallest and simplest training set and our classifier head converged after less than 500 epochs of training. In machine learning an epoch refers to the network going through the entire training set once. Depending on the size of the training set compared to the complexity of the network, CNNs usually require thousands of epochs to converge but since most of our network is pre-trained and we have a small dataset ours converged with relatively little training required.

In order to validate the accuracy of our classifier we kept 20% of the data in our training set separate to be used as a validation set and did not allow the network to see these images during training. After convergence the accuracy of the network was measured on the validation set and it was able to correctly classify 98% of the images correctly as either containing an apple or not.

Figure 7. An example image from the apple orchard dataset.

Figure 8. A small subset of the training data for the apple dataset is shown here. [1] indicates a positive match for the presence of an apple while [0] indicates background.

Next we wanted to test the networks ability to localise objects using the methods described in the previous section. We used canopy images from the validation dataset and generated bounding boxes based on the last convolution layer in the network. The resulting bounding boxes for one of the images are shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Bounding boxes generated using our localiser trained on apples.

We also tested our fruit localiser on a larger dataset of images captured in a vineyard over a period of two weeks. From these images we made 2 datasets: one for training consisting of 95 images, and another for testing consisting of 52 images. In order to test the model's robustness to changing ambient light, images from the testing set were captured on different days and under different ambient light conditions than those in the training set. This large dataset required more training but also managed to converge in less than 1000 epochs of training and could correctly classify 99% of the areas of interest in the testing image set as either containing one or more grape bunches or not.

Training this network on a more diverse and larger dataset resulted in improved detection and localisation results as can be seen in Figure 10. In this example there were very few matches falsely detected grape bunches and nowhere did the network fail to detect a real grape bunch. The bounding boxes are also more accurate in general and better represents the area where grape bunches are present.

Figure 10. Bounding boxes generated using our localiser trained on grape bunches.

Conclusion

Our primary objective in this early stage of the project was to implement a prototype fruit detection algorithm that takes advantage of the recent success that CNNs have shown in challenging image classification problems. Our system had to be robust to changing ambient light conditions and various degrees of partial occlusion. It also had to be scale and rotation invariant as the fruit we want to detect can be visible in any orientation and varies in size as the fruit matures and at different depths in the canopy.

Our implementation takes advantage of publically available pre-trained CNNs and uses the InceptionV3 network as a generic image feature extractor to base the classifier part of our model on. We then turn our classifier into a rough localiser by using the output from an intermediate layer in the network that still contains sufficient spatial information in the form of a grid of feature vectors. Each element in this grid is classified separately and the result is associated with the corresponding area in the image.

The results of our testing of this model were encouraging and showed that this approach could be sufficiently accurate and robust to be used in a yield estimation system. However, there are limitations that need to be addressed and is being investigated as future work. Firstly, the classification results can be greatly improved by training on larger more diverse datasets. This will help to prevent the false matches that are seen in several places in the results of Figure 9.

Additionally, we currently rely on high level features generated by the full InceptionV3 model. This model was designed for complex multi-class classification while we are using it for relatively simple binary classification. This suggests that lower level features extracted from earlier layers in the model may be more appropriate to base our classifier on. Not only will features from earlier layers include more spatial information increasing the resolution of our localiser, but they also take less time to calculate improving processing speed.

Once these potential improvements have been investigated it is important to test the accuracy of our system by comparing yield estimates to manually harvested yield counts instead of inspection of the image results. Some fruit will be completely occluded in the image data leading to underestimations of yield even when all visible fruit in the images have been correctly detected by the localiser.

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